

Supplementary Segment

Straining our Security

Shifting the security, developer, and developmental practitioner professions towards building an understanding of technology component security and cybersecurity practitioner roles.

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Abstract

This article introduces a holistic definition for cybersecurity; enabling our organizational end-users to safely, securely, and efficiently engage our organizational technology. We formed this definition through critical deconstructive analysis of roles within the various countermeasure component level securities, then organizing them in a way designed to assist the lay people with identifying the key differences between technology security versus cybersecurity roles. We aim to link commonly recognized security practitioner classifications, like the information security color wheel, into academically taught concepts to train the base of required technicians.

Keywords: technology component security practitioners, holistically defining cybersecurity practitioners, information security color wheel, deconstruction of technology security roles

Introduction

In 2019 the United States lost \$6.7 trillion, with \$5.7 trillion of the total attributed to losses associated with the people specifically the end-user countermeasures (Ponemon Institute, 2019). Human Resources (HR) staff often simply purchase a video to conduct training, seldom based security requirements rather the training is often based upon compliance requirements, as most users have experienced in the workplace. This may in part be due to not having sufficient security technicians in place to properly train end-users. These training roles are currently being filled by HR staff with little or no security training experience in the field of security. Per CompTIA, 75% of infrastructure and up to 98% of security technicians are missing from roles in securing infrastructure and technology within organizations (CompTIA, 2015). Infrastructure is the term used to describe the internal equipment used to carry information within an organization, while cybersecurity (or Information Assurance) involves enabling people or end-users to safely operate technology within the context of their organization (Information Technology, 2020; Kissel, 2013; Frenzel & McAndrew, 2023; Frenzel & McAndrew, 2022a; Frenzel & McAndrew, 2022b). It is unlikely the current training models have capacity to alleviate the pressures caused by missing technicians, as the field continues

to expand to cover even more singular component security fields, yet still denying the existing requirement for a holistic field of study (Frenzel & McAndrew, 2023; Frenzel & McAndrew, 2022a; Frenzel & McAndrew, 2022b).

Method

Research was performed via an integrative literature review to identify methods of classification for technology component security countermeasures versus holistic cybersecurity. Through an analysis of existing literature, leveraging a varied sampling frame, resulting in an in-depth portrayal of the concepts of technology component security countermeasures and holistic cybersecurity (Whittemore & Knaf, 2005). Different academic groups identify cybersecurity as technical component security as a means of selling academic programs and technological concepts as it seems to be more mainstream.

Discussion

Security technicians go missing for various reasons, in this case there was a lack of concerted efforts to train these security experts in lieu of training infrastructure technicians. The State of Texas uses the Workforce Enhancement Course Manual or *WECM* to categorize security as related to Infrastructure or Information Technology or *IT* hence the overall rubric of Information Technology Security or *ITSY* (THECB, 2021). Many academic instructors define cybersecurity within the scope of information technology thus information technology security, not the other technology domains addressed by IEEE or ACM (CC 2020 Task Force, 2020; Cyber2yr2020 Task Group, 2020; Joint Task Force on Cybersecurity Education, 2018; Patnayakuni & Patnayakuni, 2020; The Joint ACM/AIS MSIS 2016 Task Force, 2016). Currently there are 16 active courses that fall within the *ITSY* Rubric in *WECM* (THECB, 2021). In comparison there are 361 active courses that address configuration of specific IT equipment in different environments either as *ITXX* *excluding* *ITSY*, *HITT*, or *CPMT* (THECB, 2021). From this perspective, IT security is being overtrained while cybersecurity is rarely touched, essentially 4% of all IT courses relate to security.

Cybersecurity encompasses three countermeasures; people, processes, and technology but there is a need to further identify where the organizational security team members sit, for instance will the security practitioner interact with organizational end-users or will they interact with the back-end developers (Sosin, 2018; Maconachy et al, 2001). Once it has been determined that a specific type of security practitioner is needed, further detail is needed to determine which priority will be given to development, operations, and finally security. The order of which these priorities are listed by the organization is what the organizational leadership see as priority for activity.

Each recognized component has a specific component level security associated with it as explained in figure 1, such as IT security. Each component security is associated with a technology present in the organization. End users interact with component level technologies and therefore must interact with component level security specialists who must be able to adequately engage the organizational end users.

Cybersecurity is a subset of Information Assurance (IA), not technology, and according to IBM and the Ponemon Institute, both of which study root causality for data breaches, fewer than 5% of data breaches are caused by a failure of IT equipment, with 15% caused by process failures and 80% caused by people intentionally bypassing security protocols (IBM Security, 2020; Ponemon Institute, 2019). IA is composed of five key components; integrity, confidentiality, availability, authentication, and non-repudiation and is interrelated as shown in figure 2 (Sosin, 2018; Maconachy et al, 2001).

Sosin Cube explaining Information Assurance as created by Maconachy, Schou, and Ragsdale

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More emphasis should be directed toward identifying potential failures within people or processes rather than solely focusing on technology. The arrangement and coordination of these components dictate the specific subset of IA being addressed. For instance, information defense involves integrity and confidentiality, information security (infosec) pertains to data, and cybersecurity encompasses integrity, confidentiality, and availability. (Sosin, 2018; Maconachy et al, 2001). By rotating the cube 90 degrees, we identify a completely different focus and more importantly identify a possible way to focus our security practitioners (Frenzel & McAndrew, 2023). This rotation is visualized in figure 3.

Cybersecurity technicians are trained in the key tenants of confidentiality, integrity, and availability and are cursorily trained in IT operations to know how to navigate the organizational network. Cybersecurity is defined as all actions taken to protect organizational cyber assets, which can include administrative policies (such as sign in sheets at a data center or actively monitoring a network), physical controls, and even posted security guards (Kissel, 2013). This limited amount of training somehow justifies IT managers, hiring these technicians as infrastructure technicians, while truly trained infrastructure technicians are told that they will need to undergo cyber training to compete in the organization.

This “repurposing of the worker” is a direct challenge to the identity of the worker who has spent several years training for a career which is often tied directly to their own personal identity, this tying of a profession to an identity is often referred to as **workism**, (Thompson, 2021). This research exposes placement of IA/Cyber technicians in Infrastructure roles tends to lead to IA/Cyber technicians leaving the career field, further compounding the worker shortage. The toll demanded of IA technicians when placed in an information technology role is an emotional demand most IA technicians are unwilling to pay, therefore, they leave the field never to return, believing all IA work is akin to IT work (Tsai and Cheng, 2012).

Recently, there has been a growth within the developer community where once again developers who specialize in security are considered as cybersecurity technicians. This is consistent with what occurred originally with IT Security practitioners, in fact per CSEC 2017 we can again expect this to occur as once Data Science begins to formalize security within its ranks (Joint Task Force on Cybersecurity Education, 2018; Cyber2yr2020 Task Group, 2020; Frenzel and McAndrew, 2023). This was best drawn by Stacy Wright at Blackhat 2017, who introduced the information security color wheel as depicted below (Wright, 2017). The infosec color wheel has been rearranged and labeled with developmental teams on the left-hand side and operational teams on the right-hand side in figure 4.

Gartner Information Technology is a global consulting organization that has a reputation built on delivering guidance and knowledge about services and products within the technology space for over 40 years (Gartner, 2024a). This market presence provides a basis for their understanding of Security, Operations, and IT Operations. These definitions are commonly used and understood by businesses around the world as core functions.

IT Operations - Gartner defines IT operations as the people and management processes associated with IT service management to deliver the right set of services at the right quality and at competitive costs for customers (Gartner, 2024d).

Software Development - Project management, specifications, design, programming, testing, installation and training associated with a specific application development project of any size (Gartner, 2024f).

Security - Security is the combination of people, policies, processes, and technologies employed by an enterprise to protect its cyber and physical assets. Security is optimized to levels that business leaders define, balancing the resources required with usability/manageability and the amount of risk offset (Gartner, 2024e).

More importantly, the interrelationship between the operational, technology and security components can be visualized as a "T" overlay which can be visually represented as in figure 5.

Technology Specific Component "Security", not for the End-user.

This can then be applied to the Infosec Color wheel so that a direct relationship or correlation is visualized as in figure 6.

Technology Specific "Security", not Cybersecurity

A primary function may be combined with a secondary function to further expand upon an organization's role. This leads to roles such as DevSec, SecDev, DevOps, SecOps, OpsDev, or OpSec; depending upon how an organization sees its own role within the marketplace, as seen in table 1.

Listed order is established by Organization aka		
What is Organizational Developer to Operational technology priority?		
Primary Focus	Secondary Focus	Is Called (Known as)
Development	Security	DevSec
Development	Operations	DevOps
Operations	Development	OpsDev
Operations	Security	OpSec
Security	Operations	SecOps
Security	Development	SecDev

This primary and secondary combination creates a new form of technical role focused on a modified understanding of the terminology. For instance, Gartner (2024b) defines DevOps as:

“DevOps represents a change in IT culture, focusing on rapid IT service delivery through the adoption of agile, lean practices in the context of a system-oriented approach. DevOps emphasizes people (and culture), and it seeks to improve collaboration between operations and development teams. DevOps implementations utilize technology — especially automation tools that can leverage an increasingly programmable and dynamic infrastructure from a life cycle perspective.”

This binary combination does not include all possibilities within the Technological Security, Operational, and Developmental worlds. As is clearly shown, combining the three elements together forms a completely new developmental, operational, and technology specific security, that is still not quite the sought holistic cybersecurity, as this typically addresses specializations within technology, as demonstrated in table 2.

Listed order is established by Organization aka			
What is Organizational Developer to Operational technology priority?			
Primary Focus	Secondary Focus	Tertiary Focus	Is Called (known as)
Development	Security	Operations	DevSecOps
Development	Operations	Security	DevOpsSec
Operations	Development	Security	OpsDevSec
Operations	Security	Development	OpsSecDev
Security	Operations	Development	SecOpsDev
Security	Development	Operations	SecDevOps

In this case, Gartner (2024c) has already defined DevSecOps as:

“DevSecOps is the integration of security into emerging agile IT and DevOps development as seamlessly and as transparently as possible. Ideally, this is done without reducing the agility or speed of developers or requiring them to leave their development toolchain environment.”

Conclusion

The misidentification of security technicians within the technology component as cybersecurity professionals persists and will likely persist as long as the definition of cybersecurity remains strictly confined to technology without addressing more challenging questions. Rather than solely focusing on technology, the pertinent inquiries should center on the organizational necessity for security technicians. Technicians and technical component security practitioners avoid interfacing with the single largest source of security failure – the user. This is not blaming the user, but rather the security practitioners who avoid interacting and building an emotionally safe space for users to engage the security team without embarrassment.

To fully be a cybersecurity technician, the end-user of the technology must be integrated in a safe manner with our organizational technology. Effectively, a better understandable definition for cybersecurity is “enabling our organizational end-users to efficiently, safely, and securely engage our organizational technology”. As an educational structure, most schools or even regions claim to provide cybersecurity training, though they are often providing specific component security training programs. Each cybersecurity programs focus on specific countermeasures, but these programs often fail to provide the entire socio-technical system encompassing the entire set of people, processes, and technology security countermeasures or provide a minimalistic level of holistic training.

Suggestions

To better address this, call a technical component security technician a security technician, as identified by the organizational direction. Do not lump all security technicians together as a single set of cybersecurity technicians, instead call them as Stacy Wright so eloquently stated a team member based upon their functionality (Wright, 2017). More importantly, recognize these specialists are now hybrid specialists, they are better than a generalist in their fields. Much as a heart surgeon is better at heart surgery than a general practitioner.

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